

Delphi consensus study – Round 2

We thank all those who contributed to the first round and welcome you to this second round. During this round, you are to validate treatment goals, treatment stages, expected domains of changes and endpoints. We also would like to know in which stage you expect these changes to occur. Finally, we need you to link suggestions of expected domains of changes to standard behavioural determinants. This round includes 59 questions. They are organized in thirteen sections. Each section ends with the list of detailed responses we received during the first round. Completing the form requires approximatively 30-60 minutes.

Comment: Some participants had difficulties competing the questionnaire using Windows Explorer (e.i. not able to continue to next section). Their problem was solved by changing browser and using Chrome.

* Required

1. Please provide your StudyID : *

.....

Treatment goals

Treatment goals are separated in "long term goals", "short term goals", and "continuous goals". Within this framework, the process of driving cessation is seen as a progressive change.

Long term goals correspond to what is expected to change at the end of the entire process which can last up to six months. Therapeutic goals of the entire process are to ensure mental and physical well-being, maintain meaningful occupations, favor social engagements in the community, and assure road safety.

Short term goals correspond to expected changes at the end of each stage (Endpoints). At the end of Stage1-"Consideration", clients are expected to be able to project themselves in the future and anticipate changes in their mobility, see changes as something necessary and positive for their own future, and recognise their capability to change. At the end of Stage2-"Acceptance", clients are expected to formulate in their own words the reasons for discontinuing driving, be emotionally and rationally convinced that such a change is necessary, and accept driving retirement and the necessity of transition as their own decision. At the end of Stage3-"Action", clients are expected to make voluntary , informed decision with/without caregiver/family on alternatives, develop a transportation plan and set goals. At the end of Stage4-"Integration", clients are expected to regain autonomy in the management of their mobility with the help of their caregiver/family/community support.

Continuous goals are priorities that need to be accounted for by the "facilitator" throughout the process. The facilitator is expected to acknowledge the client's feelings toward driving cessation, guide the client through their psychological adjustment in becoming a non-driver, help the client manage grief/depression, and ensure that maximum remediation and adaptation has been tried.

Figure 1: Therapeutic goals

2. How relevant do you find the defined therapeutic goals (Description & Figure 1) ?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Irrelevant	<input type="radio"/>	Completely relevant									

3. Do you have any critics (positive or negative) or comments to add for the provided definition and representation of "treatment goals"?

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

Your submitted responses (optional reading)

A. Long term goals

A1. Mental and physical well-being

MOBILE511 : Take care of depressive symptoms after driving cessation.

MOBILE4380 : Identify if they have supportive family who live locally.

MOBILE3032 : Adequate discussion and psychosocial support available for adaptation into a different lifestyle for both retired driver and family care giver e.g. alternative but safe transportation, disposal of vehicle, return of driver licence, managing grief reaction from driving, identity & role loss as well as confronting issues associated with ageing (transition into a frailer stage?) .

MOBILE5446 : Ensuring clients maintain their current level of physical and social functioning once having given up driving.

MOBILE8925 : On completion of intervention the client will be able to: Identify and safely use a variety of private and public transport methods in order to participate in occupations of meaning in the community (e.g productivity, leisure, ADLs) in a manner that is culturally acceptable to that person use walking as a daily physical activity to achieve occupations and attain health benefits define their new non-driving identity in a manner that is meaningful to them in their context.

A2. Maintaining meaningful occupations

MOBILE8925 : On completion of intervention the client will be able to: Identify and safely use a variety of private and public transport methods in order to participate in occupations of meaning in the community (e.g productivity, leisure, ADLs) in a manner that is culturally acceptable to that

person use walking as a daily physical activity to achieve occupations and attain health benefits define their new non-driving identity in a manner that is meaningful to them in their context.
 MOBILE8255 : Maintaining community engagement - or at least identifying key activities and occupations that are important to the person.

A3. Engagement in community

MOBILE5446 : Ensuring clients maintain their current level of physical and social functioning once having given up driving.

MOBILE8925 : On completion of intervention the client will be able to: Identify and safely use a variety of private and public transport methods in order to participate in occupations of meaning in the community (e.g productivity, leisure, ADLs) in a manner that is culturally acceptable to that person use walking as a daily physical activity to achieve occupations and attain health benefits define their new non-driving identity in a manner that is meaningful to them in their context.

MOBILE8255 : Maintaining community engagement - or at least identifying key activities and occupations that are important to the person.

MOBILE7564 : Older driver's engagement in community.

MOBILE6211 : Participation in valued roles/activities.

A4. Road safety

MOBILE7564 : Safety of individual and community.

MOBILE6211 : Promoting safe mobility.

B. Short time goals

B1. Consideration

MOBILE3032 : It is part of a process of change prepared for rather than due to dire circumstances (lack of insight, denial, need to cancel the licence on medical grounds).

MOBILE5118 : Precise assesment, explaining.

MOBILE1394 : To anticipate forward planning in progressive cognitive disorders.

B2. Acceptance

MOBILE3776 : Using principles of health literacy, explaining why client needs to cease driving to family and client. Have client repeat information in his or her own words.

MOBILE4380 : Does the individual understand the reason/s why they need to cease driving.

MOBILE4380 : Is the family/ treating practitioner aware go the issues identified which means the client is recommended to cease driving.

MOBILE2503 : Awareness of the reason to discontinue driving.

MOBILE2503 : Acceptance of driver retirement.

MOBILE7125 : Establish if the person is fit to continue driving or not through the completion of a comprehensive assessment to inform the decision on fitness to drive and driving cessation.

MOBILE7125 : How aware is the person of their own ability, what level of cognition, insight/awareness do they have, for example if they are being advised to cease driving will they be 'compliant' with that advice ?

MOBILE8741 : It is difficult to provide treatment goals, as they need to be negotiated with the client and their family, and also are dependent on each specific situation. I would rather propose here things that I would consider in my first assessment, like the occupational profile, the meaning of driving, and usability of alternate mobility options, for example.

B3. Action - Exploring alternatives

MOBILE7564 : Evidence based decision making.

MOBILE3032 : Ideally it should be a voluntary , informed decision by client with/without caregiver/family

MOBILE3776 : Develop a transportation plan with client and family agreeable to all.

MOBILE8255 : Learning about alternative transport options and practical experience using them - gaining both confidence and competence.

MOBILE7125 : How dependent is the person on being able to drive? If the person is to cease driving what alternative transport options are available and how skilled is the person is using these alternative transport options.

MOBILE5446 : Developing practical strategies to meet future transportation needs.

MOBILE1394 : To promote multi-modality of transport as early as possible in the course of illness.

MOBILE8925 : On completion of intervention the client will be able to: Identify and safely use a

variety of private and public transport methods in order to participate in occupations of meaning in the community (e.g productivity, leisure, ADLs) in a manner that is culturally acceptable to that person use walking as a daily physical activity to achieve occupations and attain health benefits define their new non-driving identity in a manner that is meaningful to them in their context.

C. Continuous goals - Psychological adjustment

MOBILE1394 : To ensure that maximum remediation and adaptation has been tried.

MOBILE8255 : Psychological adjustment to becoming a non-driver - this should be individualized for the person and their specific needs.

MOBILE3776 : Acknowledge the client’s feelings toward driving cessation.

MOBILE6211 : Managing adjustment (including managing grief/depression).

MOBILE5446 : Supporting clients as they may move through a grieving process (e.g. loss of identity and independence).

MOBILE3776 : Acknowledge the client’s feelings toward driving cessation. Maybe this is what endpoint 4 is saying.

MOBILE5118 : Taking care of depressive symptoms after.

Stages and endpoints

In the four following sections, you will be asked to evaluate the relevance of the definitions of stages and endpoints.

Stage 1 - "Consideration"

This stage sees clients being confronted by the reality of their health condition and the difficulties this might lead to. Clients are engaged to discuss about potential future scenario of failing health and impact on driving abilities. They can be confronted to the difficulties they experience whilst driving. They thereby become aware that driving will no longer be possible in a close future. With a better understanding of the problem, the decision to cease driving shifts from an imposed external constraint to self-responsibility. Clients are confronted to positive experiences. They are brought to understand and manage normal grieving process positively, consider the advantage of finding alternative mode of transport, and believe in their capabilities; thereby making the idea of change possible. This stage ends once clients are aware of their advantages of giving up driving and their personal resources (Endpoint 1).

4. How relevant do you find the definition of Stage 1 and its endpoint ?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Irrelevant	<input type="radio"/>	Completely relevant									

5. Do you have any critics (positive or negative) or comments to add for the provided definition of "Stage1"?

.....

Your submitted responses (optional reading)

A. Comprehension

MOBILE1394 : Not clear what the first endpoint means.

MOBILE8741 : Endpoint 1 actually has two ideas and might be confusing as such.

B. Family

MOBILE4380 : A lot of my clients who need to cease driving do not have insight into there abilities

or lack of abilities. This is usually the reason why they have not ceased driving themselves and are required to have an assessment. The family often end up making the decisions for the client.

C. Use of term “advantages”

MOBILE8255 : I find endpoint 1 troubling as I cannot see how being aware of advantages will be helpful or a good endpoint - it may be the use of the word "advantages". Understanding the influences of ageing and the governing legislation are important - appreciating that this occurs to others is important. Is endpoint 1 intended to be about knowledge and advocacy ?

D. Preparation to change

MOBILE5446 : Understanding the system - Supporting older adults that have not voluntarily made the decision to stop driving, rather have been identified as medically at-risk and have had their licenses suspended. Helping them to understand the legal and medical aspects of this decision will ease the transition.

MOBILE7125 : Being aware of the need to consider driving cessation being adequately prepared for driving cessation, having an appropriate supported transition period.

MOBILE8255 : I would suggest the following for consideration: Something about the identity/psychological aspect - being ok about not driving and not seeing this as a negative or a failure. This is about acceptance and/or adjustment.

MOBILE3032 : Be willing to be engaged to discuss about potential future scenario of failing health and impact on driving abilities/find relevant material or resources on the topic/speak to an expert e.g. driving assessor/medical doctor or be aware of peers who have made a positive transition - before driving cessation. The ability to understand and manage normal grieving process positively - during and after driving cessation.

Stage 2 - "Acceptance"

This phase has clients make the decision of transition their own. Clients are brought to accept their need for change. They can create their own narrative for their personal reasons for discontinuing driving and be emotionally and rationally convinced that such a change is necessary. This stage ends once clients own the decision of transition (Endpoint 2).

6. How relevant do you find the definition of Stage 2 and its endpoint ?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Irrelevant	<input type="radio"/>	Completely relevant									

7. Do you have any critics (positive or negative) or comments to add for the provided definition of "Stage2"?

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

Your submitted responses (optional reading)

MOBILE8925 : Creating their own narrative of change cultural adaptation.

MOBILE8925 : Accepting grief and loss as part of process naming identity adaptations able to

explain and define plans to others, including family (e.g. adult children).

Stage 3 - "Action"

This phase has clients discover and explore possible alternatives to chose those that are most adapted in maintaining meaningful occupations. Clients develop planning skills and learn to set goals. They discuss transport options with family, caregivers or community support. They are provided with support in developing a feasible plan for how they will implement these changes, and in problem-solving unforeseen circumstances. This stage ends once clients are able to set a feasible plan for implementing adapted alternative solutions (Endpoint 3).

8. How relevant do you find the definition of Stage 3 and its endpoint ?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Irrelevant	<input type="radio"/>	Completely relevant									

9. Do you have any critics (positive or negative) or comments to add for the provided definition of "Stage3"?

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

Your submitted responses (optional reading)

A. Reformulation

MOBILE8741 : Endpoint 3 needs more negotiating idea in the word used.

B. Others

MOBILE1394 : Discussion with family and/or friends on transport options.

MOBILE5446 : Advanced Planning - Before the transition to driving cessation, older adults should be supported in developing a feasible plan for how they will implement these changes (e.g. if there is a need to relocate their living arrangements), and what transportation they will use in the future.

MOBILE5446 : Testing the alternatives - During the transition to driving cessation, older adults should begin trying to use various other transportation resources so they are familiar with them before they are completely dependent on these other options.

MOBILE5446 : Addressing unpredictable challenges - After the older adult has committed to making the change and has begun the process, they should be supported in problem-solving unforeseen circumstances.

MOBILE8255 : I found that I was unsure of some of the phrasing used in the endpoints above so have assumed that endpoint 3 means that they have chosen and are confident and competent in using an alternative means of transport. This means that I am uncertain of what endpoint 4 refers to ? I would also comment that although owning the decision is important in a successful transition - not all older drivers will do this. They may get to a point of acceptance but some may never own the decision due to the circumstances.

Stage 4 - "Integration"

This phase has patients integrate implemented changes in behaviour. This longer phase consists of a follow-up period (maximum 6 months) during which solutions are adjusted and patients integrate new habits through repetition. There is also a progressive decrease in assistance as patients recover their autonomy in choosing appropriate strategies to get to the places they want to. Self-monitoring is used to have clients implement their plan efficiently (e.i.maintain participation in valued community activities, as good as before occupational balance and well-being). This stage ends once clients are able to self-manage their mobility without further help from the facilitator (Endpoint 3).

10. How relevant do you find the definition of Stage 4 and its endpoint ?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Irrelevant	<input type="radio"/>	Completely relevant									

11. Do you have any critics (positive or negative) or comments to add for the provided definition of "Stage4"?

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

12. Changes

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

Your submitted responses (optional reading)

A. Comprehension - Reformulation - Mesurability

MOBILE3776 : I do not fully understand what this means.

MOBILE8741 : Acknowledging changes are integrated isn't clear enough for me, also difficult to see how to measure this endpoint both from the client's perspective and the therapist's. It definitely needs reformulating.

B. Participation and engagement

MOBILE8255 : I would see that the final endpoint is not about integrating changes but rather about maintaining community mobility and lifestyle. eg. Participating in all valued community activities with alternate transport.

MOBILE7564 : Developing a plan to maintain satisfying engagement in one's community.

MOBILE8741 : I think that the transition should bring at least an as good as before occupational

balance and well-being. Better if this occupational well-being is improved.
 MOBILE6211 : Maintaining participation and community engagement.

Validation of the construct

In this section, you are asked to consider the definitions provided for each stage (four previous sections) and the Figure 2 to validate the structure of the overall process.

Figure 2: Steps and Endpoints defined in MOBiLe consensus and equivalence in other models

13. How relevant do you find the construct of stages and endpoints (Figure 2) to define the process for transport transition?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Irrelevant	<input type="radio"/>	Completely relevant									

14. Do you have any critics (positive or negative) or comments to add concerning the construct of stages and endpoints for the procedure?

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

Theoretical models

Models have been identified to define the stages of the process, to structure expected domains of change, and to consider approaches to achieve endpoints. It has been noted that expecting important behavioural changes in older adults can be challenging given the Continuity Theory of Normal Ageing (Atchley 1989).

Stages of the process

To define the stages of the process, we opted for the Transtheoretical Model of Behaviour Change (Prochaska & DiClemente 1983), the Health Action Process Approach (Schwarzer 2008), closely related to the Self-efficacy Theory (Bandura 1977), and the Driving Cessation Process Model (Liddle & al. 2008).

Expected domains of change

To structure expected domains of change, we used the behaviour determinants defined within the Behavioural Change Technique taxonomy developed by Michie, Abraham, Cane and Wood (Michie et al. 2015).

Approaches to achieve endpoints (to be improved)

The problem of driving cessation and transport transition is approached using the Person Environment Occupation Model (Law et al. 1996). Behaviour change techniques that are to be used can rely on many different underlying theory including Theory of Reasoned Action, Social Learning Theory, Social Cognitive Theory, Cognitive Adaptation Theory, Goal Theory, Self-regulation Theory, Intrinsic Motivation Theories, and Self-determination Theory (Michie et al. 2010). Retained specific theoretical models are The Risk as Feeling Model (Lowenstein 2001) to be used during Stage1-“Consideration”, and the model of Selection, Optimisation, and Compensation (Baltes 1997) for goal setting during Stage3-“Action”.

15. How relevant and complete do you find the core theoretical models used to construct the procedure ?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Irrelevant	<input type="radio"/>	Completely relevant									

16. Do you have any critics (positive or negative) or comments to add for the "underlying theoretical model"?

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

Your submitted responses (optional reading)

A. Introduction

MOBILE3776 : Continuity Theory of Aging.

B. Stages of the process

MOBILE3032 : Process of change (Prochaska).

MOBILE3032 : Driving cessation process (Liddle).

MOBILE3776 : Transtheoretical Model.

MOBILE3776 : Health Action Process Approach.

MOBILE5446 : Self-Efficacy Theory (Bandura 1977).

MOBILE5446 : Stages of Change and Transtheoretical Model (Prochaska, 1983).

MOBILE8255 : Transtheoretical Model of Behavior Change.

C. Approaches to achieve endpoints (to be improved)

MOBILE3032 : Resilience model.

MOBILE3032 : SOC model of adaptation (Baltes 1997).

MOBILE3032 : Forced vs Voluntary Retirement (van Solinge & Henkens).

MOBILE3776 : Theory of Reasoned Action.

MOBILE5446 : Canadian Model of Occupational Performance and Engagement.

MOBILE5446 : Canadian Occupational Performance Measure (COPM) - to elaborate on occupational activities and resources they use to perform them.

MOBILE5446 : Often encouraging a group-based approach is also helpful with regards older adults providing each other with peer support.

MOBILE5446 : Risks as Feelings Model (Lowenstein 2001).

MOBILE5446 : Social Learning Theory (Miller 1941).

MOBILE5446 : Precaution Adoption Process Model (Weinstein 1988).

MOBILE6211 : Assessment of readiness for mobility transition (ARMT) literature is helpful. Adult education models and chronic disease self management models help to underpin an approach where people share what they know and their lived experiences and concerns with peers and experts in the area. UQDRIVE uses these approaches including peer leader approaches or the direct experiences of other older people. At this time, approaches that help people gain realistic insight into their own abilities (driving and using alternatives), graded for successful experience is also helpful.

MOBILE8255 : Person Environment Occupation Model.

MOBILE8255 : Selection, Optimization, Compensation.

Expected domains of changes**Domains of changes**

Domains of changes	Description	Examples
Relocation	Modifying destination for occupation or place of residency to improve accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Move out (to avoid if possible) Change shopping center Move in with family caregiver
Transport	Using alternative means of transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adaptation to public transports Accept transportation assistance (family / carpooling) Individual mean : scooter (if suitable)
Occupation	Maintain and prioritize meaningful activities and abandon others that are less (patient's choice)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Change in a way to maintain satisfaction Shop online Relinquish driving holidays
Social interactions	Maintaining social engagement in community and modify accessibility to social interactions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using phone, Skype or Facetime Moving interactions to more easily accessible locations Feeling free of being a burden to relatives
Emotional attachments	Addressing and recognizing the notion of loss and grief, and dependence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Changing perception of driving cessation (positive) Addressing change of identity (car owner → pedestrian) Including attachments to places and objects
Cognitive process	Improving memory, attention and decision processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improving awareness of capabilities Improving ability to plan strategies for mobility
Extrapersonal	Exploring effects of driving cessation on the family members and community support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Family members taking new roles Adult children providing transportation Redefining community service support

17. How relevant do you find the description of domains of changes ?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Irrelevant Completely relevant

18. Do you have any critics (positive or negative) or comments to add for the provided framework for change domains?

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

Your submitted responses (optional reading)

A. Changes in relocation

Aa. Aspects of occupation

MOBILE7564 : If current residence is isolated from alternative transportation, consider moving to transportation accessible community OR exploring new destinations/services on available transportation route.

MOBILE6211 : Relocation/moving where you live, and moving where you may choose to travel to - by changing aspects of occupations and activities

MOBILE7125 : Change of places of destination - changing the places the person visits, for example maybe changing where they decide to do their shopping. If they are no longer driving they may not have the same choices in where they visit or do their business and may have to change to places that are accessible by whatever alternative transport options that are available to them as a non-driver.

MOBILE2503 : Moving house or changing place of activity to allow access via alternative means.

Ab. Move out

MOBILE8255 : This implies moving home and or changing where the person is choosing to travel to each day. This would only be a final resort and one that we would explore last and only if there were no other options.

MOBILE2503 : Moving house or changing place of activity to allow access via alternative means.

MOBILE5446 : As the older adult to consider whether they would be better off moving from a rural location, closer to an urban location where there are more transportation options. It could also mean relocating closer to family, frequently visited destinations, or supported residences (e.g. retirement homes with shuttle services).

MOBILE4380 : To relocate to an area so they are near to family supports. To relocate to an area where there is good local services.

MOBILE5118 : find a place closer to the stores

MOBILE8925 : In order to ensure continued capacity to engage in the community and meet their needs, the client may move to a location or housing option that is nearer to accessible public transport, within walking distance of shops and other community supports, is supported by services such as in an independent living unit complex

MOBILE7125 : change of residency - moving from their current home, for example maybe moving from a rural area to a suburban or urban area with better alternative transport options, moving closer to family who will provide transportation.

MOBILE6211 : Relocation/moving where you live, and moving where you may choose to travel to - by changing aspects of occupations and activities

Ac. Avoid change if possible

MOBILE7125 : Having to move place of residency is a very significant development, ideally this really would require long term planning and a majority of people probably do not plan for this type of option, so it can often be a devastating and traumatic process.

MOBILE3776 : I would try to avoid changes of residency or places of destination as I support aging in place. However, sometimes this is not possible. I would try to help the client find the least restrictive environment so that desired occupations are still available if at all possible. I would help the person/family find a place that supports current/desired occupations.

MOBILE8741 : This means the person either changes the start point or the end point of the travelling. Be aware that moving for anyone, but mostly for older adults bring a high level of stress and loses familiarity in the close environment.

MOBILE3032 : Changes in residency would generally involve possibility of moving in to live or spending more time at another family member's residence, esp. for drivers who suffer from declining cognitive impairment or physical frailty that warrants some supervision or more assistance, and the said family member is open to taking a more active caregiver role to the older person/ex driver and allow the older person to live with them. Otherwise, the older person will choose to age in place in their own home, but with alternative arrangements made for him/her to access normal places of destination. For older drivers who have self regulated their driving over the years they generally have settled to a few, very familiar destinations, that matched their lifestyle.

B. Transport

Ba. Public transports

MOBILE5118 : adaptation to a public transport

MOBILE8741 : Change in the means of travelling, from car to bus, tram, train, bike or walking

MOBILE2503 : Reviewing suitability for alternative community mobility modes such as gopher use or public transport

MOBILE8255 : Learning to use and becoming confident and competent in using alternate means of transport eg walking, taxis, buses/trains/trams.

MOBILE3032 : Adjusting to use of public transport (bus, mrt) or use of taxis.

MOBILE8925 : In order to continue to move around their community independently or at different times of the day, client uses new modes such as public transport bus;

MOBILE5446 : Consider taking alternative forms of transportation - taxi, bus, train, cycling.

MOBILE7125 : using transport options other than driving themselves, for example public transport, taxi, family/friends providing transportation, etc

Bb. Transportation assistance

MOBILE8925 : accepts rides from friends or family; uses community buses provided by aged care service; uses an electric mobility scooter; travels at different times of the day; plans ahead more strategically for mobility; uses taxis for night travel or accepts ride; ride sharing

MOBILE5446 : Or also alternative transportation that is based on family support, carpooling, or disability transit.

MOBILE7125 : using transport options other than driving themselves, for example public transport, taxi, family/friends providing transportation, etc

MOBILE3776 : Oftentimes, people must accept that someone else will provide transportation. Habits and routines may need to be adjusted to accommodate a new way of using transportation assistance.

MOBILE6211 : Changing which transportation option is used (including pedestrian, supported, private and public transport options). May include changed patterns of use (moving to off peak etc.)

Bc. Individualized alternative means of transport

MOBILE2503 : gopher use

MOBILE8741 : bike or walking

MOBILE8925 : uses an electric mobility scooter

MOBILE4380 : If suitable to look at a motorised mobility aid such as a scooter

Bd. Adapted to the person

MOBILE1394 : Highly individualized: nil specific

MOBILE7564 : One transportation alternative may not fit all needs. Matching options to destinations/needs. Example: Bus to senior center, private car to lunch with friends.

MOBILE4380 : If mobile to use public transport, the local bus service. If suitable to look at a motorised mobility aid such as a scooter. Family members or friends to assist by driving the relative around. To look at community volunteer drivers.

C. Occupation

Ca. Global change

MOBILE1394 : Changes in religious practice

MOBILE7125 : changing or altering the activities outside of the home that the person engages in, including work activities, social/leisure activities. Driving cessation is likely to have an impact on how the person spends their time, they may have to change the community based activities they engage in or change their pattern of engagement in these activities.

MOBILE2503 : Modifying daily activities completed

Cb. Prioritisation : Keeping meaningful activities

MOBILE8255 : This implies changing the daily activities that a person chooses to engage in. I do not see this as an ideal endpoint as this should be the final aim/endpoint of the program ie for people to retain meaningful participation in the occupations that are important to them.

MOBILE8741 : Changing what people do. People drive because they need and want to go somewhere, they go somewhere to do something. But an occupation is more than doing, it is being and becoming, too. So by changing the occupations, meanings and satisfaction need to be preserved.

MOBILE5446 : Changes in family dynamics (other family members taking on new roles - e.g. wife becoming primary driver), providing information on the process of losing your licence (e.g. cognitive tests, legal regulations, role of the therapist), brainstorming strategies to maintain status quo of living situation (e.g. ordering meals on wheels, or primary support caregivers).

Cc. Prioritisation : Give-up activities

MOBILE3032 : Encouragement is given to maintain as many previous 'occupation' or activities as much as possible but the older person may choose to give up some activities deemed unnecessary when weighing up convenience or dependency issues on others for alternative mobility, and any impact of financial constraints.

MOBILE7564 : There is potential for changes in ability to engage in meaningful occupations with driving cessation. Acknowledgement of these changes and exploring the client's desire to maintain engagement in some occupations is needed. Client may be willing to decrease or eliminate engagement in some occupations but not others. Choice should be the client's.

MOBILE8925 : Due to loss of driving capacity the client adapts patterns and habituation by relinquishing roles that rely on driving e.g. volunteering or transporting grandchildren; accepts home delivery services or shops online; uses electronic banking services; shops locally in smaller loads or more frequently; relinquishes driving holidays

Cd. Consider new roles

MOBILE5446 : Reconsider work roles, volunteer roles, extracurricular activities, and focus on life roles that influence community mobility (e.g. grandmother involved in care of grandchildren, volunteer driver for meal truck, bus driver), in terms of distance from residency and frequency of travel.

MOBILE6211 : Undertaking different occupations, roles and activities - this often relates to surrendering the driving role and roles dependent on driving role. New roles should be considered and supported.

D. Social interactions

Da. Loss of freedom

MOBILE5446 : Driving cessation might encourage more interaction with peers and family members (travelling together). Alternatively, it may decrease social interactions by limiting frequency of contact with others. However, this must be approached with caution as many older adults avoid the potential of becoming burdensome.

MOBILE7125 : As Q14. The person may have less autonomy and freedom in deciding WHEN to engage in their chosen social interactions

Db. Use of alternative means of interactions

MOBILE3776 : Social interactions also contribute to longevity and mental health. Educating a client's social network about staying in contact is essential. Oftentimes, clients do not have access to a telephone for long distance calls in a skilled nursing facility (SNF). Since family may not live nearby, it is essential that the ability to call family is available. I have also seen clients in SNF not be able to reach/access a ringing phone.

MOBILE7564 : Exploring technology to remain socially engaged (e.g., Facetime, Skype). One senior told me she enjoyed the social interactions of public transportation. Another stated she made new friends by joining the senior center which offered some alternative transportation options.

Dc. Modify accessibility

MOBILE4380 : To transfer to interactions nearer to their home or on an alternative transport route.

MOBILE2503 : Modifying how social engagements occur - adapting to occur from more easily accessible locations

MOBILE8741 : Changes in the people you meet and talk to, do things with.

MOBILE8255 : Changing who they meet and interact with on a daily basis - as per Q14 this should be the final endpoint with an aim to retain or identify acceptable alternatives.

MOBILE5118 : develop interaction with others to be transported

Dd. Maintain social engagement (social capital)

MOBILE6211 : Alterations in the ways in which people interact with others in their environment.

This may be enhanced by alternative transport use or working in with others for private transport.

Would be negatively influenced by isolation or reduction in community mobility and engagement.

MOBILE3032 : Unlikely if retired driver has good family and social support network, willing to fetch him etc.

MOBILE8925 : Due to altered patterns of mobility previously afforded by a motor vehicle, and if mobility transition is poor, the client may become socially isolated and experience reduced or altered social engagement

E. Emotional attachments

Ea. Feeling of safety

MOBILE5118 : danger to be a pedestrian

Eb. Positive perception of change

MOBILE7125 : Changes in Mood, and changes in Independent living ?

MOBILE3032 : Impact on perception/meaning of ageing following driver retirement

MOBILE7564 : Changes in mood (positive and negative) - driving cessation may result in decrease anxiety (i.e., less stress by not driving), increased feelings of loss and possible depression.

MOBILE8925 : changes in identity formation / understanding of self e.g I am a driver; I am a

walker; I don't own a car rather I support the environment etc changes in motivation to do e.g. driving enables me to do, now I can't drive I can't be bothered, it's all too hard changes in cultural participation

MOBILE8255 : I would think that changing how the person feels about not driving any longer is an important one here - changing the perception that it is a negative outcome. Perhaps this is what you are referring to in Q16? There is an over emphasis of practical changes here and I wonder if there needs to be some more points related to the psychological aspects?

MOBILE6211 : Time use - the daily patterns of activity participation and energy use.

Understanding, accepting and planning for these changes can assist with acceptability of alternative transport use with its waiting times and lack of choice.

Ec. Changing relationships with others

MOBILE6211 : Changes to relationships with others. May be either enhanced or negatively

affected by driving cessation. Related to this would also be mood disorders/wellbeing/quality of life.

Ed. Loss of autonomy

MOBILE7125 : similar to Q16, the person's level of social interaction may decrease as they may not have the autonomy/freedom to decide WHEN to engage in social activities with others. They may also become more the dependent person in the relationship as they may be reliant on others to provide transportation.

MOBILE4380 : Demonstrate that other modes of transport are as independent making as driving a car.

Ed. Attachment to places

MOBILE3776 : Objects have the feature of providing emotional attachments. Sometimes, having pictures of these objects helps with the need for attachment. Visiting places of emotional attachment is also of value and should be considered in a transportation plan.

Ef. Loss and grief process

MOBILE5446 : Engaging in adjusting to loss of identity and driving privilege, and responding to the various stages of bereavement (e.g. denial, anger, depression, acceptance, maintenance, etc.)

MOBILE3032 : recognising grief process, losing the car, driver licence and identity related issues and personal coping strategies to manage it positively

MOBILE7564 : While technology can replay some social contact the physical isolation can result in changes to friendships and family relationships. Important to acknowledge the 'loss' the older adult may experience.

MOBILE5118 : depressive symptoms after stopping driving

MOBILE8925 : After driving cessation, a person whose identity is concerned with car ownership or car status may grieve the loss of the object / identity of driver; a person may be angry with or withdraw from a loved one who endorses the cessation of driving

Eg, Others

MOBILE8255 : Not sure of what you mean here? Is this about adjustment?

MOBILE1394 : Highly individualized: nil specific

MOBILE8741 : Things become more or less important, it is the way persons relate to things they do or things they own, like their car.

MOBILE2503 : ---

F. Cognitive process

MOBILE5446 : Changes in family dynamics (other family members taking on new roles - e.g. wife becoming primary driver), providing information on the process of losing your licence (e.g. cognitive tests, legal regulations, role of the therapist), brainstorming strategies to maintain status quo of living situation (e.g. ordering meals on wheels, or primary support caregivers).

G. Extrapersonal

Ga. Community support

MOBILE2503 : Change in formal community support services

Gb. Influence in family dynamics

MOBILE3776 : Effects on a spouse's transportation needs if the spouse relies on the impaired person's ability to provide transportation. It is usually more than one person affected by driving cessation. Also, explore the added burden to adult children providing transportation. Just recently, a woman was suppose to pick up her mother from out patient occupational therapy. She encountered a problem at work and could not leave when she needed to. The out patient clinic has to remain open past hours to wait for the daughter to show up. They thought about having the patient sit outside on a bench to wait!

MOBILE5446 : Changes in family dynamics (other family members taking on new roles - e.g. wife becoming primary driver), providing information on the process of losing your licence (e.g. cognitive tests, legal regulations, role of the therapist), brainstorming strategies to maintain status quo of living situation (e.g. ordering meals on wheels, or primary support caregivers).

Link domain of change to behavioural determinants

A behaviour determinant (BD) is a behavioural change we would expect to be able to measure following a behavioural change technique using the BCT taxonomy (Michie 2015). Please indicate to which behaviour determinant (BD) you would link each domain of change we have described in the previous table (expected changes using an occupational approach).

(more than one behaviour determinant can apply)

Only provide an answer when you are certain. For those of you who are not familiar with this type of classification, you can skip to the next section (scroll down and click on "next").

19. Relocation - Change place of occupation

Check all that apply.

- 1. Knowledge : An awareness of the existence of something.
- 2. Skills: An ability or proficiency acquired through practice.
- 3. Social/Professional Role and Identity: A coherent set of behaviours and displayed personal qualities of an individual in a social or work setting.
- 4. Beliefs about Capabilities: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about an ability, talent, or facility that a person can put to constructive use.
- 5. Optimism: The confidence that things will happen for the best or that desired goals will be attained.
- 6. Beliefs about Consequences: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about outcomes of a behaviour in a given situation.
- 7. Reinforcement: Increasing the probability of a response by arranging a dependent relationship, or contingency, between the response and a given stimulus.
- 8. Intentions: A conscious decision to perform a behaviour or a resolve to act in a certain way.
- 9. Goals: Mental representations of outcomes or end states that an individual wants to achieve.
- 10. Memory, Attention and Decision Processes: The ability to retain information, focus selectively on aspects of the environment and choose between two or more alternatives.
- 11. Environmental Context and Resources: Any circumstance of a person's situation or environment that discourages or encourages the development of skills and abilities, independence, social competence, and adaptive behaviour.
- 12. Social influences: Those interpersonal processes that can cause individuals to change their thoughts, feelings, or behaviours.
- 13. Emotion: A complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioural, and physiological elements, by which the individual attempts to deal with a personally significant matter or event.
- 14. Behavioral Regulation: Anything aimed at managing or changing objectively observed or measured actions.

20. Relocation - Move out (exceptional)

Check all that apply.

- 1. Knowledge : An awareness of the existence of something.
- 2. Skills: An ability or proficiency acquired through practice.
- 3. Social/Professional Role and Identity: A coherent set of behaviours and displayed personal qualities of an individual in a social or work setting.
- 4. Beliefs about Capabilities: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about an ability, talent, or facility that a person can put to constructive use.
- 5. Optimism: The confidence that things will happen for the best or that desired goals will be attained.
- 6. Beliefs about Consequences: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about outcomes of a behaviour in a given situation.
- 7. Reinforcement: Increasing the probability of a response by arranging a dependent relationship, or contingency, between the response and a given stimulus.
- 8. Intentions: A conscious decision to perform a behaviour or a resolve to act in a certain way.
- 9. Goals: Mental representations of outcomes or end states that an individual wants to achieve.
- 10. Memory, Attention and Decision Processes: The ability to retain information, focus selectively on aspects of the environment and choose between two or more alternatives.
- 11. Environmental Context and Resources: Any circumstance of a person's situation or environment that discourages or encourages the development of skills and abilities, independence, social competence, and adaptive behaviour.
- 12. Social influences: Those interpersonal processes that can cause individuals to change their thoughts, feelings, or behaviours.
- 13. Emotion: A complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioural, and physiological elements, by which the individual attempts to deal with a personally significant matter or event.
- 14. Behavioral Regulation: Anything aimed at managing or changing objectively observed or measured actions.

21. Transport - Public Transports

Check all that apply.

- 1. Knowledge : An awareness of the existence of something.
- 2. Skills: An ability or proficiency acquired through practice.
- 3. Social/Professional Role and Identity: A coherent set of behaviours and displayed personal qualities of an individual in a social or work setting.
- 4. Beliefs about Capabilities: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about an ability, talent, or facility that a person can put to constructive use.
- 5. Optimism: The confidence that things will happen for the best or that desired goals will be attained.
- 6. Beliefs about Consequences: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about outcomes of a behaviour in a given situation.
- 7. Reinforcement: Increasing the probability of a response by arranging a dependent relationship, or contingency, between the response and a given stimulus.
- 8. Intentions: A conscious decision to perform a behaviour or a resolve to act in a certain way.
- 9. Goals: Mental representations of outcomes or end states that an individual wants to achieve.
- 10. Memory, Attention and Decision Processes: The ability to retain information, focus selectively on aspects of the environment and choose between two or more alternatives.
- 11. Environmental Context and Resources: Any circumstance of a person's situation or environment that discourages or encourages the development of skills and abilities, independence, social competence, and adaptive behaviour.
- 12. Social influences: Those interpersonal processes that can cause individuals to change their thoughts, feelings, or behaviours.
- 13. Emotion: A complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioural, and physiological elements, by which the individual attempts to deal with a personally significant matter or event.
- 14. Behavioral Regulation: Anything aimed at managing or changing objectively observed or measured actions.

22. Transport - Transportation Assistance

Check all that apply.

- 1. Knowledge : An awareness of the existence of something.
- 2. Skills: An ability or proficiency acquired through practice.
- 3. Social/Professional Role and Identity: A coherent set of behaviours and displayed personal qualities of an individual in a social or work setting.
- 4. Beliefs about Capabilities: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about an ability, talent, or facility that a person can put to constructive use.
- 5. Optimism: The confidence that things will happen for the best or that desired goals will be attained.
- 6. Beliefs about Consequences: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about outcomes of a behaviour in a given situation.
- 7. Reinforcement: Increasing the probability of a response by arranging a dependent relationship, or contingency, between the response and a given stimulus.
- 8. Intentions: A conscious decision to perform a behaviour or a resolve to act in a certain way.
- 9. Goals: Mental representations of outcomes or end states that an individual wants to achieve.
- 10. Memory, Attention and Decision Processes: The ability to retain information, focus selectively on aspects of the environment and choose between two or more alternatives.
- 11. Environmental Context and Resources: Any circumstance of a person's situation or environment that discourages or encourages the development of skills and abilities, independence, social competence, and adaptive behaviour.
- 12. Social influences: Those interpersonal processes that can cause individuals to change their thoughts, feelings, or behaviours.
- 13. Emotion: A complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioural, and physiological elements, by which the individual attempts to deal with a personally significant matter or event.
- 14. Behavioral Regulation: Anything aimed at managing or changing objectively observed or measured actions.

23. Transport - Suitability

Check all that apply.

- 1. Knowledge : An awareness of the existence of something.
- 2. Skills: An ability or proficiency acquired through practice.
- 3. Social/Professional Role and Identity: A coherent set of behaviours and displayed personal qualities of an individual in a social or work setting.
- 4. Beliefs about Capabilities: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about an ability, talent, or facility that a person can put to constructive use.
- 5. Optimism: The confidence that things will happen for the best or that desired goals will be attained.
- 6. Beliefs about Consequences: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about outcomes of a behaviour in a given situation.
- 7. Reinforcement: Increasing the probability of a response by arranging a dependent relationship, or contingency, between the response and a given stimulus.
- 8. Intentions: A conscious decision to perform a behaviour or a resolve to act in a certain way.
- 9. Goals: Mental representations of outcomes or end states that an individual wants to achieve.
- 10. Memory, Attention and Decision Processes: The ability to retain information, focus selectively on aspects of the environment and choose between two or more alternatives.
- 11. Environmental Context and Resources: Any circumstance of a person's situation or environment that discourages or encourages the development of skills and abilities, independence, social competence, and adaptive behaviour.
- 12. Social influences: Those interpersonal processes that can cause individuals to change their thoughts, feelings, or behaviours.
- 13. Emotion: A complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioural, and physiological elements, by which the individual attempts to deal with a personally significant matter or event.
- 14. Behavioral Regulation: Anything aimed at managing or changing objectively observed or measured actions.

24. Transport - Individualized mean of alter

Check all that apply.

- 1. Knowledge : An awareness of the existence of something.
- 2. Skills: An ability or proficiency acquired through practice.
- 3. Social/Professional Role and Identity: A coherent set of behaviours and displayed personal qualities of an individual in a social or work setting.
- 4. Beliefs about Capabilities: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about an ability, talent, or facility that a person can put to constructive use.
- 5. Optimism: The confidence that things will happen for the best or that desired goals will be attained.
- 6. Beliefs about Consequences: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about outcomes of a behaviour in a given situation.
- 7. Reinforcement: Increasing the probability of a response by arranging a dependent relationship, or contingency, between the response and a given stimulus.
- 8. Intentions: A conscious decision to perform a behaviour or a resolve to act in a certain way.
- 9. Goals: Mental representations of outcomes or end states that an individual wants to achieve.
- 10. Memory, Attention and Decision Processes: The ability to retain information, focus selectively on aspects of the environment and choose between two or more alternatives.
- 11. Environmental Context and Resources: Any circumstance of a person's situation or environment that discourages or encourages the development of skills and abilities, independence, social competence, and adaptive behaviour.
- 12. Social influences: Those interpersonal processes that can cause individuals to change their thoughts, feelings, or behaviours.
- 13. Emotion: A complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioural, and physiological elements, by which the individual attempts to deal with a personally significant matter or event.
- 14. Behavioral Regulation: Anything aimed at managing or changing objectively observed or measured actions.

25. Occupation - Priorisation : keeping meaningful activities

Check all that apply.

- 1. Knowledge : An awareness of the existence of something.
- 2. Skills: An ability or proficiency acquired through practice.
- 3. Social/Professional Role and Identity: A coherent set of behaviours and displayed personal qualities of an individual in a social or work setting.
- 4. Beliefs about Capabilities: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about an ability, talent, or facility that a person can put to constructive use.
- 5. Optimism: The confidence that things will happen for the best or that desired goals will be attained.
- 6. Beliefs about Consequences: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about outcomes of a behaviour in a given situation.
- 7. Reinforcement: Increasing the probability of a response by arranging a dependent relationship, or contingency, between the response and a given stimulus.
- 8. Intentions: A conscious decision to perform a behaviour or a resolve to act in a certain way.
- 9. Goals: Mental representations of outcomes or end states that an individual wants to achieve.
- 10. Memory, Attention and Decision Processes: The ability to retain information, focus selectively on aspects of the environment and choose between two or more alternatives.
- 11. Environmental Context and Resources: Any circumstance of a person's situation or environment that discourages or encourages the development of skills and abilities, independence, social competence, and adaptive behaviour.
- 12. Social influences: Those interpersonal processes that can cause individuals to change their thoughts, feelings, or behaviours.
- 13. Emotion: A complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioural, and physiological elements, by which the individual attempts to deal with a personally significant matter or event.
- 14. Behavioral Regulation: Anything aimed at managing or changing objectively observed or measured actions.

26. Occupation - Priorisation : Give-up activities

Check all that apply.

- 1. Knowledge : An awareness of the existence of something.
- 2. Skills: An ability or proficiency acquired through practice.
- 3. Social/Professional Role and Identity: A coherent set of behaviours and displayed personal qualities of an individual in a social or work setting.
- 4. Beliefs about Capabilities: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about an ability, talent, or facility that a person can put to constructive use.
- 5. Optimism: The confidence that things will happen for the best or that desired goals will be attained.
- 6. Beliefs about Consequences: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about outcomes of a behaviour in a given situation.
- 7. Reinforcement: Increasing the probability of a response by arranging a dependent relationship, or contingency, between the response and a given stimulus.
- 8. Intentions: A conscious decision to perform a behaviour or a resolve to act in a certain way.
- 9. Goals: Mental representations of outcomes or end states that an individual wants to achieve.
- 10. Memory, Attention and Decision Processes: The ability to retain information, focus selectively on aspects of the environment and choose between two or more alternatives.
- 11. Environmental Context and Resources: Any circumstance of a person's situation or environment that discourages or encourages the development of skills and abilities, independence, social competence, and adaptive behaviour.
- 12. Social influences: Those interpersonal processes that can cause individuals to change their thoughts, feelings, or behaviours.
- 13. Emotion: A complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioural, and physiological elements, by which the individual attempts to deal with a personally significant matter or event.
- 14. Behavioral Regulation: Anything aimed at managing or changing objectively observed or measured actions.

27. Occupation - Consider new roles

Check all that apply.

- 1. Knowledge : An awareness of the existence of something.
- 2. Skills: An ability or proficiency acquired through practice.
- 3. Social/Professional Role and Identity: A coherent set of behaviours and displayed personal qualities of an individual in a social or work setting.
- 4. Beliefs about Capabilities: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about an ability, talent, or facility that a person can put to constructive use.
- 5. Optimism: The confidence that things will happen for the best or that desired goals will be attained.
- 6. Beliefs about Consequences: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about outcomes of a behaviour in a given situation.
- 7. Reinforcement: Increasing the probability of a response by arranging a dependent relationship, or contingency, between the response and a given stimulus.
- 8. Intentions: A conscious decision to perform a behaviour or a resolve to act in a certain way.
- 9. Goals: Mental representations of outcomes or end states that an individual wants to achieve.
- 10. Memory, Attention and Decision Processes: The ability to retain information, focus selectively on aspects of the environment and choose between two or more alternatives.
- 11. Environmental Context and Resources: Any circumstance of a person's situation or environment that discourages or encourages the development of skills and abilities, independence, social competence, and adaptive behaviour.
- 12. Social influences: Those interpersonal processes that can cause individuals to change their thoughts, feelings, or behaviours.
- 13. Emotion: A complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioural, and physiological elements, by which the individual attempts to deal with a personally significant matter or event.
- 14. Behavioral Regulation: Anything aimed at managing or changing objectively observed or measured actions.

28. Social interactions - Regain of sensation of freedom

Check all that apply.

- 1. Knowledge : An awareness of the existence of something.
- 2. Skills: An ability or proficiency acquired through practice.
- 3. Social/Professional Role and Identity: A coherent set of behaviours and displayed personal qualities of an individual in a social or work setting.
- 4. Beliefs about Capabilities: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about an ability, talent, or facility that a person can put to constructive use.
- 5. Optimism: The confidence that things will happen for the best or that desired goals will be attained.
- 6. Beliefs about Consequences: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about outcomes of a behaviour in a given situation.
- 7. Reinforcement: Increasing the probability of a response by arranging a dependent relationship, or contingency, between the response and a given stimulus.
- 8. Intentions: A conscious decision to perform a behaviour or a resolve to act in a certain way.
- 9. Goals: Mental representations of outcomes or end states that an individual wants to achieve.
- 10. Memory, Attention and Decision Processes: The ability to retain information, focus selectively on aspects of the environment and choose between two or more alternatives.
- 11. Environmental Context and Resources: Any circumstance of a person's situation or environment that discourages or encourages the development of skills and abilities, independence, social competence, and adaptive behaviour.
- 12. Social influences: Those interpersonal processes that can cause individuals to change their thoughts, feelings, or behaviours.
- 13. Emotion: A complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioural, and physiological elements, by which the individual attempts to deal with a personally significant matter or event.
- 14. Behavioral Regulation: Anything aimed at managing or changing objectively observed or measured actions.

29. Social interactions - Use of alternative means of interactions

Check all that apply.

- 1. Knowledge : An awareness of the existence of something.
- 2. Skills: An ability or proficiency acquired through practice.
- 3. Social/Professional Role and Identity: A coherent set of behaviours and displayed personal qualities of an individual in a social or work setting.
- 4. Beliefs about Capabilities: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about an ability, talent, or facility that a person can put to constructive use.
- 5. Optimism: The confidence that things will happen for the best or that desired goals will be attained.
- 6. Beliefs about Consequences: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about outcomes of a behaviour in a given situation.
- 7. Reinforcement: Increasing the probability of a response by arranging a dependent relationship, or contingency, between the response and a given stimulus.
- 8. Intentions: A conscious decision to perform a behaviour or a resolve to act in a certain way.
- 9. Goals: Mental representations of outcomes or end states that an individual wants to achieve.
- 10. Memory, Attention and Decision Processes: The ability to retain information, focus selectively on aspects of the environment and choose between two or more alternatives.
- 11. Environmental Context and Resources: Any circumstance of a person's situation or environment that discourages or encourages the development of skills and abilities, independence, social competence, and adaptive behaviour.
- 12. Social influences: Those interpersonal processes that can cause individuals to change their thoughts, feelings, or behaviours.
- 13. Emotion: A complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioural, and physiological elements, by which the individual attempts to deal with a personally significant matter or event.
- 14. Behavioral Regulation: Anything aimed at managing or changing objectively observed or measured actions.

30. Social interactions - Modify accessibility

Check all that apply.

- 1. Knowledge : An awareness of the existence of something.
- 2. Skills: An ability or proficiency acquired through practice.
- 3. Social/Professional Role and Identity: A coherent set of behaviours and displayed personal qualities of an individual in a social or work setting.
- 4. Beliefs about Capabilities: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about an ability, talent, or facility that a person can put to constructive use.
- 5. Optimism: The confidence that things will happen for the best or that desired goals will be attained.
- 6. Beliefs about Consequences: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about outcomes of a behaviour in a given situation.
- 7. Reinforcement: Increasing the probability of a response by arranging a dependent relationship, or contingency, between the response and a given stimulus.
- 8. Intentions: A conscious decision to perform a behaviour or a resolve to act in a certain way.
- 9. Goals: Mental representations of outcomes or end states that an individual wants to achieve.
- 10. Memory, Attention and Decision Processes: The ability to retain information, focus selectively on aspects of the environment and choose between two or more alternatives.
- 11. Environmental Context and Resources: Any circumstance of a person's situation or environment that discourages or encourages the development of skills and abilities, independence, social competence, and adaptive behaviour.
- 12. Social influences: Those interpersonal processes that can cause individuals to change their thoughts, feelings, or behaviours.
- 13. Emotion: A complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioural, and physiological elements, by which the individual attempts to deal with a personally significant matter or event.
- 14. Behavioral Regulation: Anything aimed at managing or changing objectively observed or measured actions.

31. Social interactions - Maintain social engagement

Check all that apply.

- 1. Knowledge : An awareness of the existence of something.
- 2. Skills: An ability or proficiency acquired through practice.
- 3. Social/Professional Role and Identity: A coherent set of behaviours and displayed personal qualities of an individual in a social or work setting.
- 4. Beliefs about Capabilities: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about an ability, talent, or facility that a person can put to constructive use.
- 5. Optimism: The confidence that things will happen for the best or that desired goals will be attained.
- 6. Beliefs about Consequences: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about outcomes of a behaviour in a given situation.
- 7. Reinforcement: Increasing the probability of a response by arranging a dependent relationship, or contingency, between the response and a given stimulus.
- 8. Intentions: A conscious decision to perform a behaviour or a resolve to act in a certain way.
- 9. Goals: Mental representations of outcomes or end states that an individual wants to achieve.
- 10. Memory, Attention and Decision Processes: The ability to retain information, focus selectively on aspects of the environment and choose between two or more alternatives.
- 11. Environmental Context and Resources: Any circumstance of a person's situation or environment that discourages or encourages the development of skills and abilities, independence, social competence, and adaptive behaviour.
- 12. Social influences: Those interpersonal processes that can cause individuals to change their thoughts, feelings, or behaviours.
- 13. Emotion: A complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioural, and physiological elements, by which the individual attempts to deal with a personally significant matter or event.
- 14. Behavioral Regulation: Anything aimed at managing or changing objectively observed or measured actions.

32. Emotional Attachments - Feeling of safety

Check all that apply.

- 1. Knowledge : An awareness of the existence of something.
- 2. Skills: An ability or proficiency acquired through practice.
- 3. Social/Professional Role and Identity: A coherent set of behaviours and displayed personal qualities of an individual in a social or work setting.
- 4. Beliefs about Capabilities: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about an ability, talent, or facility that a person can put to constructive use.
- 5. Optimism: The confidence that things will happen for the best or that desired goals will be attained.
- 6. Beliefs about Consequences: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about outcomes of a behaviour in a given situation.
- 7. Reinforcement: Increasing the probability of a response by arranging a dependent relationship, or contingency, between the response and a given stimulus.
- 8. Intentions: A conscious decision to perform a behaviour or a resolve to act in a certain way.
- 9. Goals: Mental representations of outcomes or end states that an individual wants to achieve.
- 10. Memory, Attention and Decision Processes: The ability to retain information, focus selectively on aspects of the environment and choose between two or more alternatives.
- 11. Environmental Context and Resources: Any circumstance of a person's situation or environment that discourages or encourages the development of skills and abilities, independence, social competence, and adaptive behaviour.
- 12. Social influences: Those interpersonal processes that can cause individuals to change their thoughts, feelings, or behaviours.
- 13. Emotion: A complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioural, and physiological elements, by which the individual attempts to deal with a personally significant matter or event.
- 14. Behavioral Regulation: Anything aimed at managing or changing objectively observed or measured actions.

33. Emotional Attachments - Positive perception of change

Check all that apply.

- 1. Knowledge : An awareness of the existence of something.
- 2. Skills: An ability or proficiency acquired through practice.
- 3. Social/Professional Role and Identity: A coherent set of behaviours and displayed personal qualities of an individual in a social or work setting.
- 4. Beliefs about Capabilities: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about an ability, talent, or facility that a person can put to constructive use.
- 5. Optimism: The confidence that things will happen for the best or that desired goals will be attained.
- 6. Beliefs about Consequences: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about outcomes of a behaviour in a given situation.
- 7. Reinforcement: Increasing the probability of a response by arranging a dependent relationship, or contingency, between the response and a given stimulus.
- 8. Intentions: A conscious decision to perform a behaviour or a resolve to act in a certain way.
- 9. Goals: Mental representations of outcomes or end states that an individual wants to achieve.
- 10. Memory, Attention and Decision Processes: The ability to retain information, focus selectively on aspects of the environment and choose between two or more alternatives.
- 11. Environmental Context and Resources: Any circumstance of a person's situation or environment that discourages or encourages the development of skills and abilities, independence, social competence, and adaptive behaviour.
- 12. Social influences: Those interpersonal processes that can cause individuals to change their thoughts, feelings, or behaviours.
- 13. Emotion: A complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioural, and physiological elements, by which the individual attempts to deal with a personally significant matter or event.
- 14. Behavioral Regulation: Anything aimed at managing or changing objectively observed or measured actions.

34. Emotional Attachments - Changing relationships with others

Check all that apply.

- 1. Knowledge : An awareness of the existence of something.
- 2. Skills: An ability or proficiency acquired through practice.
- 3. Social/Professional Role and Identity: A coherent set of behaviours and displayed personal qualities of an individual in a social or work setting.
- 4. Beliefs about Capabilities: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about an ability, talent, or facility that a person can put to constructive use.
- 5. Optimism: The confidence that things will happen for the best or that desired goals will be attained.
- 6. Beliefs about Consequences: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about outcomes of a behaviour in a given situation.
- 7. Reinforcement: Increasing the probability of a response by arranging a dependent relationship, or contingency, between the response and a given stimulus.
- 8. Intentions: A conscious decision to perform a behaviour or a resolve to act in a certain way.
- 9. Goals: Mental representations of outcomes or end states that an individual wants to achieve.
- 10. Memory, Attention and Decision Processes: The ability to retain information, focus selectively on aspects of the environment and choose between two or more alternatives.
- 11. Environmental Context and Resources: Any circumstance of a person's situation or environment that discourages or encourages the development of skills and abilities, independence, social competence, and adaptive behaviour.
- 12. Social influences: Those interpersonal processes that can cause individuals to change their thoughts, feelings, or behaviours.
- 13. Emotion: A complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioural, and physiological elements, by which the individual attempts to deal with a personally significant matter or event.
- 14. Behavioral Regulation: Anything aimed at managing or changing objectively observed or measured actions.

35. Emotional Attachments - Loss and grief process

Check all that apply.

- 1. Knowledge : An awareness of the existence of something.
- 2. Skills: An ability or proficiency acquired through practice.
- 3. Social/Professional Role and Identity: A coherent set of behaviours and displayed personal qualities of an individual in a social or work setting.
- 4. Beliefs about Capabilities: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about an ability, talent, or facility that a person can put to constructive use.
- 5. Optimism: The confidence that things will happen for the best or that desired goals will be attained.
- 6. Beliefs about Consequences: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about outcomes of a behaviour in a given situation.
- 7. Reinforcement: Increasing the probability of a response by arranging a dependent relationship, or contingency, between the response and a given stimulus.
- 8. Intentions: A conscious decision to perform a behaviour or a resolve to act in a certain way.
- 9. Goals: Mental representations of outcomes or end states that an individual wants to achieve.
- 10. Memory, Attention and Decision Processes: The ability to retain information, focus selectively on aspects of the environment and choose between two or more alternatives.
- 11. Environmental Context and Resources: Any circumstance of a person's situation or environment that discourages or encourages the development of skills and abilities, independence, social competence, and adaptive behaviour.
- 12. Social influences: Those interpersonal processes that can cause individuals to change their thoughts, feelings, or behaviours.
- 13. Emotion: A complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioural, and physiological elements, by which the individual attempts to deal with a personally significant matter or event.
- 14. Behavioral Regulation: Anything aimed at managing or changing objectively observed or measured actions.

36. Emotional Attachments - Attachment to places

Check all that apply.

- 1. Knowledge : An awareness of the existence of something.
- 2. Skills: An ability or proficiency acquired through practice.
- 3. Social/Professional Role and Identity: A coherent set of behaviours and displayed personal qualities of an individual in a social or work setting.
- 4. Beliefs about Capabilities: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about an ability, talent, or facility that a person can put to constructive use.
- 5. Optimism: The confidence that things will happen for the best or that desired goals will be attained.
- 6. Beliefs about Consequences: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about outcomes of a behaviour in a given situation.
- 7. Reinforcement: Increasing the probability of a response by arranging a dependent relationship, or contingency, between the response and a given stimulus.
- 8. Intentions: A conscious decision to perform a behaviour or a resolve to act in a certain way.
- 9. Goals: Mental representations of outcomes or end states that an individual wants to achieve.
- 10. Memory, Attention and Decision Processes: The ability to retain information, focus selectively on aspects of the environment and choose between two or more alternatives.
- 11. Environmental Context and Resources: Any circumstance of a person's situation or environment that discourages or encourages the development of skills and abilities, independence, social competence, and adaptive behaviour.
- 12. Social influences: Those interpersonal processes that can cause individuals to change their thoughts, feelings, or behaviours.
- 13. Emotion: A complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioural, and physiological elements, by which the individual attempts to deal with a personally significant matter or event.
- 14. Behavioral Regulation: Anything aimed at managing or changing objectively observed or measured actions.

37. Cognitive process

Check all that apply.

- 1. Knowledge : An awareness of the existence of something.
- 2. Skills: An ability or proficiency acquired through practice.
- 3. Social/Professional Role and Identity: A coherent set of behaviours and displayed personal qualities of an individual in a social or work setting.
- 4. Beliefs about Capabilities: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about an ability, talent, or facility that a person can put to constructive use.
- 5. Optimism: The confidence that things will happen for the best or that desired goals will be attained.
- 6. Beliefs about Consequences: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about outcomes of a behaviour in a given situation.
- 7. Reinforcement: Increasing the probability of a response by arranging a dependent relationship, or contingency, between the response and a given stimulus.
- 8. Intentions: A conscious decision to perform a behaviour or a resolve to act in a certain way.
- 9. Goals: Mental representations of outcomes or end states that an individual wants to achieve.
- 10. Memory, Attention and Decision Processes: The ability to retain information, focus selectively on aspects of the environment and choose between two or more alternatives.
- 11. Environmental Context and Resources: Any circumstance of a person's situation or environment that discourages or encourages the development of skills and abilities, independence, social competence, and adaptive behaviour.
- 12. Social influences: Those interpersonal processes that can cause individuals to change their thoughts, feelings, or behaviours.
- 13. Emotion: A complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioural, and physiological elements, by which the individual attempts to deal with a personally significant matter or event.
- 14. Behavioral Regulation: Anything aimed at managing or changing objectively observed or measured actions.

38. Extrapersonal - Community support

Check all that apply.

- 1. Knowledge : An awareness of the existence of something.
- 2. Skills: An ability or proficiency acquired through practice.
- 3. Social/Professional Role and Identity: A coherent set of behaviours and displayed personal qualities of an individual in a social or work setting.
- 4. Beliefs about Capabilities: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about an ability, talent, or facility that a person can put to constructive use.
- 5. Optimism: The confidence that things will happen for the best or that desired goals will be attained.
- 6. Beliefs about Consequences: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about outcomes of a behaviour in a given situation.
- 7. Reinforcement: Increasing the probability of a response by arranging a dependent relationship, or contingency, between the response and a given stimulus.
- 8. Intentions: A conscious decision to perform a behaviour or a resolve to act in a certain way.
- 9. Goals: Mental representations of outcomes or end states that an individual wants to achieve.
- 10. Memory, Attention and Decision Processes: The ability to retain information, focus selectively on aspects of the environment and choose between two or more alternatives.
- 11. Environmental Context and Resources: Any circumstance of a person's situation or environment that discourages or encourages the development of skills and abilities, independence, social competence, and adaptive behaviour.
- 12. Social influences: Those interpersonal processes that can cause individuals to change their thoughts, feelings, or behaviours.
- 13. Emotion: A complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioural, and physiological elements, by which the individual attempts to deal with a personally significant matter or event.
- 14. Behavioral Regulation: Anything aimed at managing or changing objectively observed or measured actions.

39. Extrapersonal - Influence in family dynamics*Check all that apply.*

- 1. Knowledge : An awareness of the existence of something.
- 2. Skills: An ability or proficiency acquired through practice.
- 3. Social/Professional Role and Identity: A coherent set of behaviours and displayed personal qualities of an individual in a social or work setting.
- 4. Beliefs about Capabilities: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about an ability, talent, or facility that a person can put to constructive use.
- 5. Optimism: The confidence that things will happen for the best or that desired goals will be attained.
- 6. Beliefs about Consequences: Acceptance of the truth, reality, or validity about outcomes of a behaviour in a given situation.
- 7. Reinforcement: Increasing the probability of a response by arranging a dependent relationship, or contingency, between the response and a given stimulus.
- 8. Intentions: A conscious decision to perform a behaviour or a resolve to act in a certain way.
- 9. Goals: Mental representations of outcomes or end states that an individual wants to achieve.
- 10. Memory, Attention and Decision Processes: The ability to retain information, focus selectively on aspects of the environment and choose between two or more alternatives.
- 11. Environmental Context and Resources: Any circumstance of a person's situation or environment that discourages or encourages the development of skills and abilities, independence, social competence, and adaptive behaviour.
- 12. Social influences: Those interpersonal processes that can cause individuals to change their thoughts, feelings, or behaviours.
- 13. Emotion: A complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioural, and physiological elements, by which the individual attempts to deal with a personally significant matter or event.
- 14. Behavioral Regulation: Anything aimed at managing or changing objectively observed or measured actions.

Linking domain of changes to stages

For each domain of change, please indicate at which stage you would expect these changes to occur when necessary.

(can occur at more than one stage)

40. Relocation - Change place of occupation*Check all that apply.*

- Stage1-"Consideration"
- Stage2-"Acceptance"
- Stage3-"Action"
- Stage4-"Integration"

41. Relocation - Move out (exceptional)*Check all that apply.*

- Stage1-"Consideration"
- Stage2-"Acceptance"
- Stage3-"Action"
- Stage4-"Integration"

42. Transport - Public Transports*Check all that apply.*

- Stage1-"Consideration"
- Stage2-"Acceptance"
- Stage3-"Action"
- Stage4-"Integration"

43. Transport - Transportation Assistance*Check all that apply.*

- Stage1-"Consideration"
- Stage2-"Acceptance"
- Stage3-"Action"
- Stage4-"Integration"

44. Transport - Suitability*Check all that apply.*

- Stage1-"Consideration"
- Stage2-"Acceptance"
- Stage3-"Action"
- Stage4-"Integration"

45. Transport - Individualized mean of alter*Check all that apply.*

- Stage1-"Consideration"
- Stage2-"Acceptance"
- Stage3-"Action"
- Stage4-"Integration"

46. Occupation - Priorisation : keeping meaningful activities*Check all that apply.*

- Stage1-"Consideration"
- Stage2-"Acceptance"
- Stage3-"Action"
- Stage4-"Integration"

47. Occupation - Priorisation : Give-up activities*Check all that apply.*

- Stage1-"Consideration"
- Stage2-"Acceptance"
- Stage3-"Action"
- Stage4-"Integration"

48. Occupation - Consider new roles*Check all that apply.*

- Stage1-"Consideration"
- Stage2-"Acceptance"
- Stage3-"Action"
- Stage4-"Integration"

49. Social interactions - Loss of freedom*Check all that apply.*

- Stage1-"Consideration"
- Stage2-"Acceptance"
- Stage3-"Action"
- Stage4-"Integration"

50. Social interactions - Use of alternative means of interactions*Check all that apply.*

- Stage1-"Consideration"
- Stage2-"Acceptance"
- Stage3-"Action"
- Stage4-"Integration"

51. Social interactions - Modify accessibility*Check all that apply.*

- Stage1-"Consideration"
- Stage2-"Acceptance"
- Stage3-"Action"
- Stage4-"Integration"

52. Social interactions - Maintain social engagement*Check all that apply.*

- Stage1-"Consideration"
- Stage2-"Acceptance"
- Stage3-"Action"
- Stage4-"Integration"

53. Emotional Attachments - Feeling of safety*Check all that apply.*

- Stage1-"Consideration"
- Stage2-"Acceptance"
- Stage3-"Action"
- Stage4-"Integration"

54. Emotional Attachments - Positive perception of change*Check all that apply.*

- Stage1-"Consideration"
- Stage2-"Acceptance"
- Stage3-"Action"
- Stage4-"Integration"

55. Emotional Attachments - Changing relationships with others*Check all that apply.*

- Stage1-"Consideration"
- Stage2-"Acceptance"
- Stage3-"Action"
- Stage4-"Integration"

56. Emotional Attachments - Loss and grief process

Check all that apply.

- Stage1-"Consideration"
- Stage2-"Acceptance"
- Stage3-"Action"
- Stage4-"Integration"

57. Emotional Attachments - Attachment to places

Check all that apply.

- Stage1-"Consideration"
- Stage2-"Acceptance"
- Stage3-"Action"
- Stage4-"Integration"

58. Cognitive process

Check all that apply.

- Stage1-"Consideration"
- Stage2-"Acceptance"
- Stage3-"Action"
- Stage4-"Integration"

59. Extrapersonal - Community support

Check all that apply.

- Stage1-"Consideration"
- Stage2-"Acceptance"
- Stage3-"Action"
- Stage4-"Integration"

60. Extrapersonal - Influence in family dynamics

Check all that apply.

- Stage1-"Consideration"
- Stage2-"Acceptance"
- Stage3-"Action"
- Stage4-"Integration"

End of Round 2

You have answered the last question. You will be invited for the next round on February 4th. To validate your answers, press the submit button on this page.

